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Survey Firm: The Roper Organization
Sponsor:
Interview Dates: September 11-18, 1993
Type of Sample: National Adult
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Weight Location: *CARD 5, Cols. 14-17*

COMMENTS:

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93-9 SEPT 1993

CF #

6- 7- 8- 9- 10- 11- 12- 13- BLOCK #

14-

STUDY #93-9 SEPT. 1993 COUNTY _____ PLACE _____ **X**5-1

AM 1 19/ AM

Time started _____ PM 2 Time finished _____ PM Total minutes _____ 20/21
15/16/17/18

I'm from The Roper Organization and we're conducting a survey about things that are happening today.

1. Considering both the availability and cost of things today, as well as your present financial circumstances, do you think now is a good time to buy things you want and need, or a good time to wait, or is it someplace in between?

Now is a good time to buy...1 Someplace in between ...3 22/
Now is a good time to wait...2 Don't knowY

2. Do you feel things in this country are generally going in the right direction today, or do you feel that things have pretty seriously gotten off on the wrong track?

Right direction.....1 Don't knowY 23/
Wrong track.....2

3. What is your opinion of most Federal Government departments and agencies? There may be exceptions, of course, but would you say your opinion of most Federal Departments and agencies is highly favorable, or moderately favorable, or not too favorable, or rather unfavorable?

Highly favorable1 24/
Moderately favorable....2
Not too favorable3
Rather unfavorable4
Don't knowY

CF #

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6- 7- 8- 9- 10- 11- 12- 13-

BLOCK #

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14-

STUDY #93-9 SEPT. 1993 COUNTY _____ PLACE _____ **Y**5-2

AM 1 19/

AM

Time started _____ PM 2 Time finished _____ PM Total minutes _____ 20/21
15/16/17/18

I'm from The Roper Organization and we're conducting a survey about things that are happening today.

1. Considering both the availability and cost of things today, as well as your present financial circumstances, do you think now is a good time to buy things you want and need, or a good time to wait, or is it someplace in between?

Now is a good time to buy...1 Someplace in between ...3 22/

Now is a good time to wait..2 Don't knowY

2. Do you feel things in this country are generally going in the right direction today, or do you feel that things have pretty seriously gotten off on the wrong track?

Right direction.....1 Don't knowY 23/

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3. What is your opinion of most Federal Government departments and agencies? There may be exceptions, of course, but would you say your opinion of most Federal Departments and agencies is highly favorable, or moderately favorable, or not too favorable, or rather unfavorable?

Highly favorable1 24/

Moderately favorable....2

Not too favorable3

Rather unfavorable4

Don't knowY

4. Now let me ask you about a few specific federal agencies. Using this card (HAND RESPONDENT CARD), first the (read item)--is your opinion of them highly favorable, moderately favorable, or not too favorable, or rather unfavorable? (ASK ABOUT EACH ONE)

	HIGHLY FAVOR- ABLE	MODER- ATELY FAVOR- ABLE	NOT TOO FAVOR- ABLE	RATHER UN- FAVOR- ABLE	DON'T KNOW	
a. F.T.C. (Federal Trade Commission)	1	2	3	4	Y	25/
b. F.B.I. (Federal Bureau of Investigation) .1		2	3	4	Y	26/
c. O.S.H.A. (Occupational Safety and Health Administration)	1	2	3	4	Y	27/
d. F.C.C. (Federal Communications Commission)	1	2	3	4	Y	28/
e. N.A.S.A. (National Aeronautic and Space Administration)	1	2	3	4	Y	29/
f. B.A.T.F. (Bureau of Alcohol, Tobacco, and Firearms)	1	2	3	4	Y	30/
g. I.R.S. (Internal Revenue Service)	1	2	3	4	Y	31/
h. F.A.A. (Federal Aviation Administration) .1		2	3	4	Y	32/

5. Here is a list of some social problems. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) For each one, please tell me if you think it affects you more, less, or the same as the average person in this country?

	MORE	LESS	ABOUT THE SAME	DON'T KNOW	
a. Violent crime	1	2	3	Y	33/
b. Pollution	1	2	3	Y	34/
c. Economic hardship	1	2	3	Y	35/
d. Police brutality	1	2	3	Y	36/
e. High taxes	1	2	3	Y	37/
f. Discrimination	1	2	3	Y	38/

6. There has been talk about whether some problems in society have more of an impact or less of an impact on racial and ethnic minorities than they have on other people. (USING SAME CARD) For each one, please tell me if you think it affects racial and ethnic minorities more, less, or about the same as other people?

	MORE	LESS	ABOUT THE SAME	DON'T KNOW	
a. Violent crime	1	2	3	Y	39/
b. Pollution	1	2	3	Y	40/
c. Economic hardship	1	2	3	Y	41/
d. Police brutality	1	2	3	Y	42/
e. High taxes	1	2	3	Y	43/
f. Discrimination	1	2	3	Y	44/

4. Now let me ask you about a few specific federal agencies. Using this card (HAND RESPONDENT CARD), first the (read item)--is your opinion of them highly favorable, moderately favorable, or not too favorable, or rather unfavorable? (ASK ABOUT EACH ONE)

	HIGHLY FAVOR- ABLE	MODER- ATELY FAVOR- ABLE	NOT TOO FAVOR- ABLE	RATHER UN- FAVOR- ABLE	DON'T KNOW	
a. F.T.C. (Federal Trade Commission)	1	2	3	4	Y	25/
b. C.I.A. (Central Intelligence Agency)	1	2	3	4	Y	26/
c. N.P.S. (National Park Service)	1	2	3	4	Y	27/
d. F.D.A. (Food and Drug Administration)	1	2	3	4	Y	28/
e. C.P.S.C. (Consumer Products Safety Commission)	1	2	3	4	Y	29/
f. O.S.A.P. (Office of Substance Abuse Prevention)	1	2	3	4	Y	30/
g. E.P.A. (Environmental Protection Agency) .	1	2	3	4	Y	31/
h. S.S.A. (Social Security Administration) ..	1	2	3	4	Y	32/

5. Here is a list of some social problems. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) For each one, please tell me if you think it affects you more, less, or the same as the average person in this country?

	MORE	LESS	ABOUT THE SAME	DON'T KNOW	
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c. Economic hardship	1	2	3	Y	35/
d. Police brutality	1	2	3	Y	36/
e. High taxes	1	2	3	Y	37/
f. Discrimination	1	2	3	Y	38/

6. There has been talk about whether some problems in society have more of an impact or less of an impact on racial and ethnic minorities than they have on other people. (USING SAME CARD) For each one, please tell me if you think it affects racial and ethnic minorities more, less, or about the same as other people?

	MORE	LESS	ABOUT THE SAME	DON'T KNOW	
a. Violent crime	1	2	3	Y	39/
b. Pollution	1	2	3	Y	40/
c. Economic hardship	1	2	3	Y	41/
d. Police brutality	1	2	3	Y	42/
e. High taxes	1	2	3	Y	43/
f. Discrimination	1	2	3	Y	44/

7. And thinking about crime in the United States, what one type of crime do you feel presents the biggest threat for you and your family today? (HAND RESPONDENT CARD)
- a. Burglary, robbery, auto theft1 45/
 - b. Vandalism/hooliganism2
 - c. Official corruption, government bribe-taking3
 - d. Murder4
 - e. Rape5
 - f. Assault6
 - g. Racketeering, extortion7
 - h. Drugs8
 - i. Prostitution9
 - j. Speculation and swindling0
 - k. Other1 46/
 - None of the above (vol.)2
 - Don't knowY

8. Of course, the problems we face in our society often have many different causes. I am going to ask you about some different problems in society and for each one I want you to tell me what you think are the major causes of each problem. First, violent crime. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Using this card, which three or four things do you think are the main causes of people committing violent crimes?

VIOLENT
CRIME

- a. Living in poverty1 47/
- b. Parents not teaching
right from wrong2
- c. Being abused as a child3
- d. Drug abuse4
- e. What people see in TV programs5
- f. A lack of morals6
- g. A lack of education7
- h. A person not seeing any harm in it ..8
- i. A person being irresponsible9
- j. Influence of friends0
- k. Alcohol abuseX
- l. What people see in moviesY
- m. The advertising and marketing
of toy guns, etc.1 48/
- n. Guns being too easy to get2
- o. Low chance of being punished3
- p. Seeing pornography4
- None of these5
- Don't knowY

9. What about drunk driving? (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Using this card, which three or four things do you think are the main causes of people becoming drunk drivers?

DRUNK
DRIVING

- a. Living in poverty1 49/
- b. Parents not teaching
right from wrong2
- c. Being abused as a child3
- d. Drug abuse4
- e. What people see in TV programs5
- f. A lack of morals6
- g. A lack of education7
- h. A person not seeing any harm in it ..8
- i. A person being irresponsible9
- j. Influence of friends0
- k. Being unable to control drinking
because alcoholism is a
diseaseX
- l. What people see in moviesY
- m. What people see in advertising1 50/
- n. Bartenders not being responsible2
- o. Low chance of being punished3
- p. Friends and family not looking
out for each other4
- None of these5
- Don't knowY

7. And thinking about crime in the United States, what one type of crime do you feel presents the biggest threat for you and your family today? (HAND RESPONDENT CARD)

- a. Burglary, robbery, auto theft1 45/
- b. Vandalism/hooliganism2
- c. Official corruption, government bribe-taking3
- d. Murder4
- e. Rape5
- f. Assault6
- g. Racketeering, extortion7
- h. Drugs8
- i. Prostitution9
- j. Speculation and swindling0
- k. Other1 46/
- None of the above (vol.)2
- Don't knowY

8. Of course, the problems we face in our society often have many different causes. I am going to ask you about some different problems in society and for each one I want you to tell me what you think are the major causes of each problem. First, teenage pregnancy. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Using this card, which three or four things do you think are the main causes that lead to unmarried teenagers becoming pregnant?

**TEENAGE
PREGNANCY**

- a. Living in poverty1 47/
- b. Parents not teaching
right from wrong2
- c. Being abused as a child3
- d. Drug abuse4
- e. What people see in TV programs5
- f. A lack of morals6
- g. A lack of education7
- h. A person not seeing any harm in it .8
- i. A person being irresponsible9
- j. Influence of friends0
- k. Alcohol abuseX
- l. What people see in moviesY
- m. What people see in advertising1 48/
- n. A lack of religion2
- o. Birth control being hard to get3
- p. Seeing pornography4
- None of these5
- Don't knowY

9. What about drug abuse? (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Using this card, which three or four things do you think are the main causes of people abusing drugs?

**DRUG
ABUSE**

- a. Living in poverty1 49/
- b. Parents not teaching
right from wrong2
- c. Being abused as a child3
- d. Being unable to control drug
use because of addiction4
- e. What people see in TV programs5
- f. A lack of morals6
- g. A lack of education7
- h. A person not seeing any harm in it .8
- i. A person being irresponsible9
- j. Influence of friends0
- k. Alcohol abuseX
- l. What people see in moviesY
- m. What people see in advertising1 50/
- n. Illegal drugs being too easy
to get2
- o. Low chance of being punished3
- p. Doctors and pharmacists over-
prescribing4
- None of these5
- Don't knowY

10. People have strong feelings about some issues, and not so strong about others. On this card (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) there is a scale of feelings--absolutely delighted, pleased, somewhat satisfied, no real feelings one way or the other, somewhat dissatisfied, angry, and boiling mad. Using this scale, how would you describe your feelings when you think about: (ASK ABOUT EACH)

	<u>1.</u> ABSOLUTELY DELIGHTED	<u>2.</u> PLEASED	<u>3.</u> SOMEWHAT SATISFIED	<u>4.</u> NO REAL FEELINGS	<u>5.</u> SOMEWHAT DISSATISFIED	<u>6.</u> ANGRY	<u>7.</u> BOILING MAD	DON'T KNOW	
a. The way things are going for you personally these days	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	51/
b. The way things are going for the country generally	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	52/
c. How President Clinton is dealing with the economy	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	53/
d. How Congress is dealing with the economy	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	54/
e. How your state government is dealing with the state's economy	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	55/
f. How secure your job is	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	56/
g. Your health care costs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	57/
h. The amount of your household income	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	58/
i. The rate of inflation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	59/
j. The amount of taxes you pay	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	60/
k. The level of interest rates	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	61/
l. The cost and value of your housing	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	62/
m. The level of your personal debts	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	63/

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	1. ABSOLUTELY DELIGHTED	2. PLEASED	3. SOMEWHAT SATISFIED	4. NO REAL FEELINGS	5. SOMEWHAT DISSATISFIED	6. ANGRY	7. BOILING MAD	DON'T KNOW	
a. The way things are going for you personally these days	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	51/
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c. How President Clinton is dealing with the economy	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	53/
d. How Congress is dealing with the economy	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	54/
e. How your state government is dealing with the state's economy	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	55/
f. How secure your job is	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	56/
g. Your health care costs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	57/
h. The amount of your household income	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	58/
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j. The amount of taxes you pay	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	60/
k. The level of interest rates	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	61/
l. The cost and value of your housing	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	62/
m. The level of your personal debts	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Y	63/

11. As you may know, the Internal Revenue Service spends a considerable amount of time dealing with the collection of taxes that are overdue. To help with this problem, the IRS is considering using outside contractors, such as law firms, accountants and collection agencies, as well as its own employees.

Do you think the IRS should use outside contractors to contact taxpayers for the purpose of explaining the options that are available for paying taxes that are past due, or should this be done only by IRS employees?

Use outside contractors .1 6/
 Done only by IRS employees2
 Doesn't matter (vol.) ...3
 Don't knowY

12. Do you think the IRS should use those outside contractors to help in the actual collection of taxes that are past due, or should this be done only by IRS employees?

Use outside contractors .1 7/
 Done only by IRS employees2
 Doesn't matter (vol.) ...3
 Don't knowY

13. If you personally owed back taxes to the IRS, would it bother you more to receive a call from an outside contractor rather than an IRS employee, or wouldn't it make a difference which one called?

Would bother me more to receive call from contractor1 8/
 Wouldn't make a difference2
 Don't knowY

14. Turning to a different subject, times today are, of course, different than when your parents were your age. But taking into account those differences, would you say that compared to your parents, you (read each item), about the same amount, or less?

	MORE	SAME	LESS	DON'T KNOW	
a. Have more fun	1	2	3	Y	9/
b. Have more success financially.....	1	2	3	Y	10/
c. Have a happier family.....	1	2	3	Y	11/
d. Work harder	1	2	3	Y	12/
e. Have more time to enjoy life.....	1	2	3	Y	13/
f. Have more stress	1	2	3	Y	14/
g. Have more wisdom	1	2	3	Y	15/

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	MORE	SAME	LESS	DON'T KNOW	
a. Have more fun	1	2	3	Y	9/
b. Have more success financially.....	1	2	3	Y	10/
c. Have a happier family.....	1	2	3	Y	11/
d. Work harder	1	2	3	Y	12/
e. Have more time to enjoy life.....	1	2	3	Y	13/
f. Have more stress	1	2	3	Y	14/
g. Have more wisdom	1	2	3	Y	15/

15. Most people find some things in their lives boring. Here is a list of some things people have said bore them. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Would you read down the list and call off the things, if any, that you personally find boring? Just call off the letters.

- | | | | | |
|--|---|-----|---|-------|
| a. Cooking | 1 | 16/ | k. The current emphasis on physical fitness | X |
| b. Housekeeping | 2 | | l. The current focus on senior citizens | Y |
| c. Grocery shopping | 3 | | m. Going to parties | 1 17/ |
| d. Paying bills, keeping records on household finances | 4 | | n. Talking on the telephone | 2 |
| e. Your job | 5 | | o. Writing letters | 3 |
| f. Economic news | 6 | | p. Yardwork | 4 |
| g. News about foreign affairs | 7 | | q. Doing household repairs | 5 |
| h. What's going on in Washington .. | 8 | | None | 6 |
| i. Sports on TV | 9 | | Don't know | Y |
| j. Most entertainment shows on TV . | 0 | | | |

16. There has been a move to change the form of address for women from Miss and Mrs. to Ms. Which form of address do you like best for women--Miss and Mrs., or Ms.?

- | | | | | |
|--------------------|---|------------------|---|-----|
| Miss and Mrs. | 1 | Don't know | Y | 18/ |
| Ms. | 2 | | | |

17. Here is a list of household tasks. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Would you read down that list, and call off each one you do at least occasionally?

		<u>18.</u>							
		<u>17.</u>	EN- JOY	DON'T MIND	DIS- LIKE SOME- WHAT	DIS- LIKE GREAT DEAL	DON'T KNOW		
		DO							
a. Shopping for food	1	19/	1	2	3	4	Y	21/	
b. Cooking meals	2		1	2	3	4	Y	22/	
c. Washing dishes	3		1	2	3	4	Y	23/	
d. Vacuuming	4		1	2	3	4	Y	24/	
e. Dusting	5		1	2	3	4	Y	25/	
f. Polishing furniture	6		1	2	3	4	Y	26/	
g. Cleaning bathroom or kitchen floors	7		1	2	3	4	Y	27/	
h. Cleaning bathtubs, shower stalls, sinks ...	8		(ASK	1	2	3	4	Y	28/
i. Cleaning toilets	9		18)	1	2	3	4	Y	29/
j. Cleaning glass, mirrors, windows	0		1	2	3	4	Y	30/	
k. Cleaning the oven	X		1	2	3	4	Y	31/	
l. Washing kitchen counters, sinks and appliances	Y	1	2	3	4	Y	32/		
m. Doing the laundry	1	20/	1	2	3	4	Y	33/	
n. Ironing	2		1	2	3	4	Y	34/	
o. Recycling (bottles, cans, paper, etc.)	3		1	2	3	4	Y	35/	
None	4	(SKIP TO 19)							
Don't know	Y								

18. Now for each of these tasks you do, would you tell me whether it is something you enjoy doing, or something you don't mind doing, or something you dislike somewhat, or something you dislike a great deal? (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) First, (name task)? (ASK ABOUT EACH TASK ANSWERED IN Q.17)

15. Most people find some things in their lives boring. Here is a list of some things people have said bore them. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Would you read down the list and call off the things, if any, that you personally find boring? Just call off the letters.

- | | | | | |
|--|---|-----|---|-------|
| a. Cooking | 1 | 16/ | k. The current emphasis on physical fitness | X |
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| c. Grocery shopping | 3 | | m. Going to parties | 1 17/ |
| d. Paying bills, keeping records on household finances | 4 | | n. Talking on the telephone | 2 |
| e. Your job | 5 | | o. Writing letters | 3 |
| f. Economic news | 6 | | p. Yardwork | 4 |
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|--------------------|---|------------------|---|-----|
| Miss and Mrs. | 1 | Don't know | Y | 18/ |
| Ms. | 2 | | | |

17. Here is a list of household tasks. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Would you read down that list, and call off each one you do at least occasionally?

		18.						
		DIS- LIKE	DIS- LIKE	SOME- WHAT	GREAT DEAL	DON'T KNOW		
17. DO	EN- JOY	DON'T MIND	WHAT	DEAL	KNOW			
a. Shopping for food	1	19/	1	2	3	4	Y	21/
b. Cooking meals	2		1	2	3	4	Y	22/
c. Washing dishes	3		1	2	3	4	Y	23/
d. Vacuuming	4		1	2	3	4	Y	24/
e. Dusting	5		1	2	3	4	Y	25/
f. Polishing furniture	6		1	2	3	4	Y	26/
g. Cleaning bathroom or kitchen floors	7		1	2	3	4	Y	27/
h. Cleaning bathtubs, shower stalls, sinks ...	8	(ASK 18)	1	2	3	4	Y	28/
i. Cleaning toilets	9		1	2	3	4	Y	29/
j. Cleaning glass, mirrors, windows	0		1	2	3	4	Y	30/
k. Cleaning the oven	X		1	2	3	4	Y	31/
l. Washing kitchen counters, sinks and appliances	Y		1	2	3	4	Y	32/
m. Doing the laundry	1	20/	1	2	3	4	Y	33/
n. Ironing	2		1	2	3	4	Y	34/
o. Recycling (bottles, cans, paper, etc.)	3		1	2	3	4	Y	35/
None	4	(SKIP TO 19)						
Don't know	Y							

18. Now for each of these tasks you do, would you tell me whether it is something you enjoy doing, or something you don't mind doing, or something you dislike somewhat, or something you dislike a great deal? (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) First, (name task)? (ASK ABOUT EACH TASK ANSWERED IN Q.17)

(ASK EVERYONE)

19. Here is a list of products. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Please call off the letters for all the ones you tend to buy when you shop in a discount store such as K mart, Wal-Mart and Caldor.

	<u>19.</u> DISCOUNT STORE	<u>20.</u> CONVENI- ENCE STORE	<u>21.</u> DRUG- STORE
a. Canned food	1 36/	1 39/	1 42/
b. Household cleaners	2	2	2
c. Hardware	3	3	3
d. Toys/games	4	4	4
e. Recorded music (tapes, CDs, etc.)	5	5	5
f. Paper products (towels, napkins, etc.)	6	6	6
g. Magazines	7	7	7
h. Beer	8	8	8
i. Cigarettes	9	9	9
j. Small appliances	0	0	0
k. Frozen foods	X	X	X
l. Cosmetics	Y	Y	Y
m. Personal care products (shampoo, deodorant, etc.) .	1 37/	1 40/	1 43/
n. Dress clothes	2	2	2
o. Casual clothes	3	3	3
p. Underwear, socks, hosiery	4	4	4
q. Shoes	5	5	5
r. Fashion accessories (scarfs, ties, belts, etc.) ...	6	6	6
s. Wine	7	7	7
t. Liquor.....	8	8	8
u. Towels, linens, sheets	9	9	9
v. Auto accessories	0	0	0
w. Soft drinks	X	X	X
x. Fruit juice	Y	Y	Y
y. Snack foods	1 38/	1 41/	1 44/
z. Take-out/ready-to-eat food	2	2	2
aa. Stationery/greeting cards	3	3	3
bb. Books	4	4	4
cc. Meat/poultry	5	5	5
dd. Cold cereals	6	6	6
ee. Cold cuts	7	7	7
ff. Housewares (pots, pans, silverware, etc.)	8	8	8
Don't shop there (vol.)	9	9	9
Don't know	Y	Y	Y

20. (USING SAME CARD) Using the same list of products would you call off the products you tend to buy when you shop in a convenience store such as 7-11, Circle K and Mobil Mart? (RECORD ABOVE)

21. (USING SAME CARD) And finally, what products do you tend to buy when you shop in a drugstore? (RECORD ABOVE)

(ASK EVERYONE)

19. Here is a list of products. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Please call off the letters for all the ones you tend to buy when you shop in a grocery store or supermarket.

	<u>19.</u> GROCERY STORE/ SUPERMARKET	<u>20.</u> DEPART- MENT STORE	<u>21.</u> WAREHOUSE STORE
a. Canned food	1 36/	1 39/	1 42/
b. Household cleaners	2	2	2
c. Hardware	3	3	3
d. Toys/games	4	4	4
e. Recorded music (tapes, CDs, etc.)	5	5	5
f. Paper products (towels, napkins, etc.)	6	6	6
g. Magazines	7	7	7
h. Beer	8	8	8
i. Cigarettes	9	9	9
j. Small appliances	0	0	0
k. Frozen foods	X	X	X
l. Cosmetics	Y	Y	Y
m. Personal care products (shampoo, deodorant, etc.) .1	37/	1 40/	1 43/
n. Dress clothes	2	2	2
o. Casual clothes	3	3	3
p. Underwear, socks, hosiery	4	4	4
q. Shoes	5	5	5
r. Fashion accessories (scarfs, ties, belts, etc.) ...	6	6	6
s. Wine	7	7	7
t. Liquor	8	8	8
u. Towels, linens, sheets	9	9	9
v. Auto accessories	0	0	0
w. Soft drinks	X	X	X
x. Fruit juice	Y	Y	Y
y. Snack foods	1 38/	1 41/	1 44/
z. Take-out/ready-to-eat food	2	2	2
aa. Stationery/greeting cards	3	3	3
bb. Books	4	4	4
cc. Meat/poultry	5	5	5
dd. Cold cereals	6	6	6
ee. Cold cuts	7	7	7
ff. Housewares (pots, pans, silverware, etc.)	8	8	8
Don't shop there (vol.)	9	9	9
Don't know	Y	Y	Y

20. (USING SAME CARD) Using the same list of products would you call off the products you tend to buy when you shop in a department store? (RECORD ABOVE)

21. (USING SAME CARD) And finally, what products do you tend to buy when you shop in a warehouse store? (RECORD ABOVE)

(ASK EVERYONE)

43. Turning now to a different subject. There are differing opinions as to how health insurance should be provided. Some people favor the present system of private insurance and health plans. Others say we should have a national system of health insurance provided through the government and paid for like Social Security now is. Which do you favor--our present system of private health plans, or a national health insurance plan provided through the government?

Present private plan	60/
National plan	
Don't know	Y

44. Thinking of all your medical care needs, not just the doctor, generally speaking, how satisfied would you say you are with the quality of the medical care you get--very satisfied, fairly well satisfied, not too satisfied, or not at all satisfied?

	<u>44.</u>		<u>45.</u>	
	QUALITY		AVAILABILITY	
	OF MEDICAL CARE		OF MEDICAL CARE	
Very satisfied.....	1	61/	1	62/
Fairly well satisfied.....	2		2	
Not too satisfied.....	3		3	
Not at all satisfied.....	4		4	
Don't know.....	Y		Y	

45. And how satisfied are you with the availability of medical care when you need it--very satisfied, fairly well satisfied, not too satisfied, or not at all satisfied? (RECORD ABOVE)

79-0
80-3

43. OMITTED.

NO COL. 60

44. Turning to a different subject, thinking of all your medical care needs, not just the doctor, generally speaking, how satisfied would you say you are with the quality of the medical care you get--very satisfied, fairly well satisfied, not too satisfied, or not at all satisfied?

	<u>44.</u> QUALITY OF MEDICAL CARE	<u>45.</u> AVAILABILITY OF MEDICAL CARE
Very satisfied.....	1 61/	1 62/
Fairly well satisfied.....	2	2
Not too satisfied.....	3	3
Not at all satisfied.....	4	4
Don't know.....	Y	Y

45. And how satisfied are you with the availability of medical care when you need it--very satisfied, fairly well satisfied, not too satisfied, or not at all satisfied? (RECORD ABOVE)

79-0
80-3

46. How do you feel about the cost of the medical care you receive--do you feel the cost is very reasonable, fairly reasonable, somewhat unreasonable, or very unreasonable?

- Very reasonable1 6/
- Fairly reasonable2
- Somewhat unreasonable...3
- Very unreasonable!.....4
- Don't know.....Y

47. How satisfied are you with the arrangements you have for paying for medical care--very satisfied, fairly well satisfied, not too satisfied, or not at all satisfied?

- Very satisfied1 7/
- Fairly well satisfied ..2
- Not too satisfied3
- Not at all satisfied ...4
- Don't know.....Y

48. Do you and your family have any type of health care plan or hospital insurance?

- Yes1 (ASK 49) 8/
- No2 (SKIP TO 56 ON NEXT PAGE)
- Some in family covered, others not (vol.)3 (ASK 49)

49. Is that paid for at least in part by your employer or some family member's employer?

- Yes1 (ASK 50) 9/
 - No2
 - Don't knowY
- (SKIP TO 52)

50. Does the employer pay all or part of the cost of that coverage?

- All1 10/
- Part2
- Don't knowY

51. About how much per month does the employer pay for your medical and health coverage?

\$ _____ 11/12/13/14
(write in)

Don't know.....Y

52. And about how much per month, if any, do you pay for your medical and health coverage?

\$ _____ 15/16/17/18
(write in)

Don't know.....Y

53. Rising health insurance premiums may require employers to reduce available health insurance benefits in future years or to reduce the amount of future pay increases in order to pay rising insurance costs. Which would you prefer--to receive the full amount of future pay increases but have health insurance benefits reduced, or to receive smaller future pay increases but keep health insurance coverage at its current level?

- Full increases, benefits reduced ..1 19/
- Smaller increases, current health coverage2
- Don't knowY

46. How do you feel about the cost of the medical care you receive--do you feel the cost is very reasonable, fairly reasonable, somewhat unreasonable, or very unreasonable?

- Very reasonable1 6/
- Fairly reasonable2
- Somewhat unreasonable...3
- Very unreasonable4
- Don't knowY

47. How satisfied are you with the arrangements you have for paying for medical care--very satisfied, fairly well satisfied, not too satisfied, or not at all satisfied?

- Very satisfied1 7/
- Fairly well satisfied...2
- Not too satisfied3
- Not at all satisfied...4
- Don't knowY

48. Do you and your family have any type of health care plan or hospital insurance?

- Yes1 (ASK 49) 8/
- No2 (SKIP TO 56 ON NEXT PAGE)
- Some in family covered, others not (vol.)3 (ASK 49)

49. Is that paid for at least in part by your employer or some family member's employer?

- Yes1 (ASK 50) 9/
 - No2
 - Don't knowY
- (SKIP TO 52)

50. Does the employer pay all or part of the cost of that coverage?

- All1 10/
- Part2
- Don't knowY

51. About how much per month does the employer pay for your medical and health coverage?

- \$ _____ 11/12/13/14
(write in)
- Don't knowY

52. And about how much per month, if any, do you pay for your medical and health coverage?

- \$ _____ 15/16/17/18
(write in)
- Don't knowY

53. Rising health insurance premiums may require employers to reduce available health insurance benefits in future years or to reduce the amount of future pay increases in order to pay rising insurance costs. Which would you prefer--to receive the full amount of future pay increases but have health insurance benefits reduced, or to receive smaller future pay increases but keep health insurance coverage at its current level?

- Full increases, benefits reduced ..1 19/
- Smaller increases, current health coverage2
- Don't knowY

54. Which of these types of health care plans, if any, do you personally have? (HAND RESPONDENT CARD)

- a. An HMO, Preferred Provider Organization (PPO), or other managed care plan where you have a limited choice of doctors1 20/
- b. A traditional insurance plan where you can choose any doctor you want2 (ASK 55)
- c. Medicare (over 65)3
- d. Veteran's Administration ...4
- e. Medicaid5
- Other (vol.)6
- None/personally not covered (vol.)7 (SKIP TO 56)
- Don't knowY (ASK 55)

55. Have you or any member of your family living with you ever been with-out a health plan in the past two years?

- Yes, went without1 (ASK 56) 21/
 - No2
 - Don't knowY
- (SKIP TO 58)

56. For how many months in the past two years have you or someone in your family not had a health plan?

- Less than 3 months1 22/
- 3 months to less than 6 months ..2
- 6 months to less than 12 months .3
- 1 year to less than 24
- 2 years (or more)5
- Don't knowY

57. OMITTED.

NO COLS.23,24

(ASK EVERYONE)

58. The cost of living has been rising steadily in recent years. Is it your impression that health care costs have been increasing a good deal more than the cost of living in general, increasing somewhat more, increasing at about the same rate, or increasing less than the cost of living in general?

- A good deal more1 25/
- Somewhat more2
- About the same3
- Less4
- Don't knowY

54. Which of these types of health care plans, if any, do you personally have? (HAND RESPONDENT CARD)
- a. An HMO, Preferred Provider Organization (PPO), or other managed care plan where you have a limited choice of doctors1 20/
 - b. A traditional insurance plan where you can choose any doctor you want2 (ASK 55)
 - c. Medicare (over 65)3
 - d. Veteran's Administration ...4
 - e. Medicaid5
 - Other (vol.)6
 - None/personally not covered (vol.)7 (SKIP TO 56)
 - Don't knowY (ASK 55)

55. Have you or any member of your family living with you ever been with-out a health plan in the past two years?
- Yes, went without1 (ASK 56) 21/
 - No2 (SKIP TO 57)
 - Don't knowY

56. For how many months in the past two years have you or someone in your family not had a health plan?
- Less than 3 months1 22/
 - 3 months to less than 6 months ..2
 - 6 months to less than 12 months .3
 - 1 year to less than 24
 - 2 years (or more)5
 - Don't knowY

- (ASK EVERYONE)
57. There are differing opinions as to how health insurance should be provided. Some people favor the present system of private insurance and health plans. Others say we should have a national system of health insurance provided through the government and paid for like Social Security now is. Which do you favor--our present system of private health plans, or a national health insurance plan provided through the government?

Present private plan..1 23/

National plan.....2

Don't know.....Y

NO COL.24

58. The cost of living has been rising steadily in recent years. Is it your impression that health care costs have been increasing a good deal more than the cost of living in general, increasing somewhat more, increasing at about the same rate, or increasing less than the cost of living in general?

A good deal more.....1 25/

Somewhat more.....2

About the same.....3

Less.....4

Don't know.....Y

59. On another subject, here is a list of different products that could be advertised on television during children's programming--such as Saturday morning, or during afternoon cartoons. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Would you please read down that list, and for each one tell me if it is something that is all right to advertise during children's programming, or not all right to advertise during children's programming? First, (read item). (ASK ABOUT EACH)

	ALL RIGHT	NOT ALL RIGHT	DEPENDS/ DON'T KNOW	
a. Toys	1	2	Y	26/
b. Children's clothes and accessories	1	2	Y	27/
c. Recorded music (CD's, tapes, etc.)	1	2	Y	28/
d. Walkman type radios or cassettes	1	2	Y	29/
e. Children's video cassettes	1	2	Y	30/
f. G-rated movies	1	2	Y	31/
g. PG-13 rated movies	1	2	Y	32/
h. Sneakers and shoes	1	2	Y	33/
i. Cereal	1	2	Y	34/
j. Candy	1	2	Y	35/
k. Public service announcements about the dangers of drugs, smoking and drinking	1	2	Y	36/
l. Public service announcements about the dangers of unsafe sex	1	2	Y	37/
m. "900" type telephone numbers (recordings of music and movie stars, trivia games, sports updates)	1	2	Y	38/

60. Which of these sources have you used in the last six months to get information on the nutritional content of food--either fresh or packaged food? (HAND RESPONDENT CARD)

	<u>60.</u> USED IN 6 MONTHS		<u>61.</u> MOST USEFUL
a. Pamphlets published by a government agency	1	39/	1 40/
b. Pamphlets prepared by food companies	2		2
c. What other people have told you about nutrition in food	3		3
d. Labels on food packages	4		4
e. ☒ Courses you took in school	5		5
f. Advertisements for food products	6		6
g. Newspaper articles	7		7
h. Magazine articles	8		8
i. Television programs	9		9
j. ☒ Cookbooks	0		0
None	X	] (SKIP TO 62)	X
Don't know	Y		Y

61. Of those you have used, which one or two of those sources have you found most useful on the nutritional content of food? (RECORD ABOVE)

59. On another subject, here is a list of different products that could be advertised on television during children's programming--such as Saturday morning, or during afternoon cartoons. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Would you please read down that list and for each one tell me if it is something that is all right to advertise during children's programming, or not all right to advertise during children's programming? First, (read item). (ASK ABOUT EACH)

	ALL RIGHT	NOT ALL RIGHT	DEPENDS/ DON'T KNOW	
a. Toys	1	2	Y	26/
b. Children's clothes and accessories	1	2	Y	27/
c. Recorded music (CD's, tapes, etc.)	1	2	Y	28/
d. Walkman type radios or cassettes	1	2	Y	29/
e. Children's video cassettes	1	2	Y	30/
f. G-rated movies	1	2	Y	31/
g. PG-13 rated movies	1	2	Y	32/
h. Sneakers and shoes	1	2	Y	33/
i. Cereal	1	2	Y	34/
j. Candy	1	2	Y	35/
k. Public service announcements about the dangers of drugs, smoking and drinking	1	2	Y	36/
l. Public service announcements about the dangers of unsafe sex	1	2	Y	37/
m. "900" type telephone numbers (recordings of music and movie stars, trivia games, sports updates)	1	2	Y	38/

60. Which of these sources have you used in the last six months to get information on the nutritional content of food--either fresh or packaged food? (HAND RESPONDENT CARD)

	<u>60.</u> USED IN 6 MONTHS	<u>61.</u> MOST USEFUL
a. Pamphlets published by a government agency	1 39/	1 40/
b. Pamphlets prepared by food companies	2	2
c. What other people have told you about nutrition in food	3	3
d. Labels on food packages	4	4
e. Restaurant menus	5	5
f. Advertisements for food products	6	6
g. Newspaper articles	7	7
h. Magazine articles	8	8
i. Television programs	9	9
j. Signs posted in restaurants	0	0
None	X	X
Don't know	Y	Y

(SKIP TO 62)

61. Of those you have used, which one or two of those sources have you found most useful on the nutritional content of food? (RECORD ABOVE)

(ASK EVERYONE)

62. Here is a list of organizations and industries. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) For each one, please tell me if it is doing an excellent job, a good job, only a fair job, or a poor job in providing nutritional information about food. First, (read item). (ASK ABOUT EACH)

	EX- CELLENT JOB	GOOD JOB	FAIR JOB	POOR JOB	DON'T KNOW	
a. Food manufacturers	1	2	3	4	Y	41/
b. Supermarkets	1	2	3	4	Y	42/
c. Fast food restaurants	1	2	3	4	Y	43/
d. Restaurants with table service	1	2	3	4	Y	44/
e. Government agencies	1	2	3	4	Y	45/
f. Public schools	1	2	3	4	Y	46/
g. The media	1	2	3	4	Y	47/

65. Turning to something else, I'd like to talk with you now about games of chance, such as the lottery, off-track betting, casino gambling, and so forth. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) For each of the types of gambling or games of chance on this card, please tell me whether or not you have done it in the past year.

	YES	NO	DON'T KNOW	
a. Played games of chance like Bingo sponsored by church groups, charitable organizations, etc.	1	2	Y	50/
b. Played any State-run lottery games	1	2	Y	51/
c. Bet on a horse race	1	2	Y	52/
d. Bet on a dog race	1	2	Y	53/
e. Bet on a Jai-Alai (HIGH-lie) game	1	2	Y	54/
f. Gambled at a casino	1	2	Y	55/
g. Played card games for money, such as poker or black jack, at a place other than a casino	1	2	Y	56/
h. Played non-legalized numbers games	1	2	Y	57/
i. Placed sports bets, such as at your place of work, in a betting parlor, or through a bookie	1	2	Y	58/

INTERVIEWER: IF ANY ITEMS CIRCLED IN BOX, ASK Q.66.
IF NO ITEMS CIRCLED IN BOX, SKIP TO Q.67.

79-0	79-0
80-4	80-5

(ASK EVERYONE)

68. Do you think government lotteries produce an unwholesome gambling spirit in this country?

Yes1

27/

No2

69. Now here is a list of a number of different things. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD)

Would you read down that list and call off each one you personally have done in the last week, either at home or at work?

- a. Gone shopping for food1
- b. Bought take-out food to eat at home2
- c. Bought a (special) food product because of its nutritional content3
- d. Bought bottled water to drink as a substitute for tap water4
- e. Used a credit card5
- f. Gone into a bank (business or personal)6
- g. Done banking by mail (business or personal)7
- h. Done banking by phone8
- i. Used an automatic teller machine9
- j. Used an ATM card to pay for a purchase0
- k. Drank decaffeinated coffeeX
- l. Drank decaffeinated tea1
- m. Drank beer2
- n. Drank wine3
- o. Drank a wine cooler4
- p. Drank liquor5
- q. Smoked cigarettes (1/2 pack or more)6
- r. Made a long distance phone call (more than 100 miles) at home or
at work7
- s. Made a collect phone call8
- t. Took bottles/cans to recycling center9
- u. Returned bottles/cans to store0
- v. Put out bottles/cans, etc., for curbside recyclingX
- w. Gone to church or religious service1
- None2
- Don't knowY

28/

29/

30/

(ASK EVERYONE)

68. Do you think government lotteries produce an unwholesome gambling spirit in this country?

Yes1

27/

No2

69. Now here is a list of a number of different things. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD)

Would you read down that list and call off each one you personally have done in the last week, either at home or at work?

- a. Gone shopping for food1
- b. Bought take-out food to eat at home2
- c. Bought a (special) food product because of its nutritional content3
- d. Bought bottled water4
- e. Used a credit card5
- f. Gone into a bank (business or personal)6
- g. Done banking by mail (business or personal)7
- h. Done banking by phone8
- i. Used an automatic teller machine9
- j. Used an ATM card to pay for a purchase0
- k. Drank decaffeinated coffeeX
- l. Drank decaffeinated tea1
- m. Drank beer2
- n. Drank wine3
- o. Drank a wine cooler4
- p. Drank liquor5
- q. Smoked cigarettes (1/2 pack or more)6
- r. Made a long distance phone call (more than 100 miles) at home or
at work7
- s. Made a collect phone call8
- t. Took bottles/cans to recycling center9
- u. Returned bottles/cans to store0
- v. Put out bottles/cans, etc., for curbside recyclingX
- w. Gone to church or religious service1
- None2
- Don't knowY

28/

29/

30/

(ASK EVERYONE)

71. After you and the other members of your household pay for all the necessities like food, rent or mortgage, utilities, and other basic bills, how much money a month, if any, do you have left over to save or spend on optional items such as gifts, entertainment, eating out, vacations, and other general purchases? (IF NOT SURE SAY: "JUST A ROUGH ESTIMATE WOULD BE FINE.")

\$.00
 42/ 43/ 44/ 45/ 46/

RefusedX

Don't knowY

79-0
80-6

72. Now I am going to ask you about non-essential spending in different categories. Without worrying how much it all adds up to right now, about how much money would you say your household spends in an average month on (read item)? If you aren't sure, just guess about how much. (ASK ABOUT EACH)

	AMOUNT	NONE	DON'T KNOW	
a. Clothing for adults ...	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y	6/7/8/9
b. Clothing for children .	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y	10/11/12/13
c. Movies, concerts, sports events	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y	14/15/16
d. Dining out	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y	17/18/19
e. Travel, weekend getaways	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y	20/21/22/23
f. Tapes, records, CDs, videos, etc.	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y	24/25/26
g. Things for the home ...	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y	27/28/29/30
h. Reading materials (books, magazines and newspapers)	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y	31/32/33
i. Savings/investments	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y	34/35/36/37/38

NO COLS. 31-41

70. OMITTED

(ASK EVERYONE)

71. After you and the other members of your household pay for all the necessities like food, rent or mortgage, utilities, and other basic bills, how much money a month, if any, do you have left over to save or spend on optional items such as gifts, entertainment, eating out, vacations, and other general purchases? (IF NOT SURE SAY: "JUST A ROUGH ESTIMATE WOULD BE FINE.")

\$.00
 42/ 43/ 44/ 45/ 46/

RefusedX

Don't knowY

79-0
80-6

72. Now I am going to ask you about non-essential spending in different categories. Without worrying how much it all adds up to right now, about how much money would you say your household spends in an average month on (read item)? If you aren't sure, just guess about how much. (ASK ABOUT EACH)

		AMOUNT		DON'T		
		NONE	KNOW			
a. Clothing for adults ...	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y			6/7/8/9
b. Clothing for children .	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y			10/11/12/13
c. Movies, concerts, sports events	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y			14/15/16
d. Dining out	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y			17/18/19
e. Travel, weekend getaways	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y			20/21/22/23
f. Tapes, records, CDs, videos, etc.	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y			24/25/26
g. Things for the home ...	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y			27/28/29/30
h. Reading materials (books, magazines and newspapers)	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y			31/32/33
i. Savings/investments	\$ <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> .00	X	Y			34/35/36/37/38

73. Now here are two views about what is responsible for the way people think and act and the type of health they have. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD)

(READ) Statement A: It's more due to heredity--that is, the traits and characteristics a person is born with.

Statement B: It's more due to environment--that is, where and how a person is raised and how he or she lives.

I'm going to read a list of some characteristics people might have. For each one, would you tell me which you think is more important in determining why people are the way they are--heredity or environment? First, (read item). Is that more due to heredity or environment? (ASK ABOUT EACH ITEM)

	HEREDITY (STATE- MENT A)	ENVIRONMENT (STATE- MENT B)	BOTH EQUALLY (VOL.)	DON'T KNOW	
a. How well a person reads	1	2	3	Y	39/
b. Whether a person is overweight or not ...	1	2	3	Y	40/
c. Whether a person is likely to have a heart attack	1	2	3	Y	41/
d. Whether someone becomes a drug addict ...	1	2	3	Y	42/
e. What kind of personality a person has ...	1	2	3	Y	43/
f. How bright or smart person is	1	2	3	Y	44/
g. Whether someone becomes a criminal	1	2	3	Y	45/
h. Whether someone becomes a great artist or musician	1	2	3	Y	46/

73. Now here are two views about what is responsible for the way people think and act and the type of health they have. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD)

(READ) Statement A: It's more due to heredity--that is, the traits and characteristics a person is born with.

Statement B: It's more due to environment--that is, where and how a person is raised and how he or she lives.

I'm going to read a list of some characteristics people might have. For each one, would you tell me which you think is more important in determining why people are the way they are--heredity or environment? First, (read item). Is that more due to heredity or environment? (ASK ABOUT EACH ITEM)

	HEREDITY (STATE- MENT A)	ENVIRONMENT (STATE- MENT B)	BOTH EQUALLY (VOL.)	DON'T KNOW	
a. How well a person reads	1	2	3	Y	39/
b. Whether a person is overweight or not ...	1	2	3	Y	40/
c. Whether a person is likely to have a heart attack	1	2	3	Y	41/
d. Whether someone becomes an alcoholic	1	2	3	Y	42/
e. Whether someone is a heterosexual or homosexual	1	2	3	Y	43/
f. Whether someone is a great athlete	1	2	3	Y	44/
g. Whether someone gets cancer	1	2	3	Y	45/
h. Whether someone becomes a great artist or musician	1	2	3	Y	46/

D-1. Thinking politically and socially, how would you describe your own general outlook--as being very conservative, moderately conservative, middle-of-the-road, moderately liberal, or very liberal?

- Very conservative 1 6/
Moderately conservative 2
Middle-of-the-road 3
Moderately liberal 4
Very liberal 5
Don't know Y

D-2. Regardless of how you may have voted in the past, what do you usually consider yourself--a Democrat, a Republican, some other party or what?

- Democrat 1 7/
Republican 2
Other specific party 3
Independent (Vol.) 4
No particular party (Vol.) ... 5
Refused 6
Don't know Y

D-3. Now here is a list of things some people do about government or politics. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Have you happened to have done any of those things in the past year? (IF "YES") Which ones?

- a. Written your Congressman or Senator 1 8/
b. Attended a political rally or speech 2
c. Attended a public meeting on town or school affairs 3
d. Held or run for political office .. 4
e. Served on a committee for some local organization 5
f. Served as an officer of some club or organization 6
g. Written a letter to the paper 7
h. Signed a petition 8
i. Worked for a political party 9
j. Made a speech 0
k. Written an article for a magazine or newspaper X
l. Been a member of some group like the League of Women Voters, or some other group interested in better government . 1 9/
No--none of these 2
Don't know Y

D-4. Are you regularly employed, either full-time or part-time?

- Full-time 1
Part-time 2
Not employed 3 (ASK D-5)
(SKIP TO D-6) 10/

D-5. Are you (CALL OFF APPROPRIATE CATEGORIES):

- A homemaker, 1
Unemployed, 2
A student, 3
Retired, 4
Or what? (all other) . Y
(SKIP TO D-7) 11/

D-6. What is your occupation?

- Executive, administrative, management 1 12/
Top talent and major or lesser professional 2
Owner--small retail store/business 3
Farmers (owners and managers) 4
Technicians, minor administrative 5
White collar, clerical (non-supervisory) .. 6
Salesmen 7
Skilled and semi-skilled labor 8
Unskilled labor 9
Service and protective workers 0

(ASK EVERYONE)

D-7. Do you, or does anyone in your family living here at home belong to a labor union?

- Respondent belongs to union 1
Other family member only belongs to union . 2
No one belongs to union 3
Don't know Y 13/

D-8. Are you married, widowed, separated, divorced or have you never been married?

- Married 1 (ASK D-9) 14/
Widowed 2
Separated or divorced . 3
Never been married 4
(SKIP TO D-10)

D-9. Is your (husband/wife) employed either full-time or part-time? (IF "YES") Which?

Employed full-time	1	15/
Employed part-time	2	
Not employed	3	

(ASK EVERYONE)

D-10. Are you a parent or not?

Yes	1	16/
No	2	

D-11. Are there any children living here at home with you: (RECORD FOR EACH CATEGORY)

Age 3 or younger? Yes . 1	No . 2	17/
Age 4 through 7? Yes . 1	No . 2	18/
Age 8 through 12? Yes . 1	No . 2	19/
Age 13 through 17? Yes . 1	No . 2	20/

D-12. Do you own your own home, rent it, or do you have some other arrangement such as living in the home of your parents or children?

Own	1	21/
Rent	2	
Live in home of parents ..	3	
Live in home of children .	4	
Other (vol.)	5	

D-13. Do you consider yourself the male/female head of this household or not?

Male head	1	22/
Female head	2	
Another adult living in the house	3	

D-14. Do you personally do most of the grocery shopping for your household, or does somebody else do most of it?

Respondent	1	23/
Somebody else	2	
Shared equally (vol.)	3	
Nobody does it (vol,)	4	
Don't know	Y	

D-15. What was the last grade of regular school that you completed--not counting specialized schools like secretarial, art or trade schools?

No school	1	24/
Grade school (1-8)	2	
Some high school (9-11) ..	3	
High school graduate (12)	4	
Some college (13-15)	5	
College graduate (16)	6	
Post graduate (17+)	7	

D-16. Here is a list of age groups. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Would you call off the letter of the age group you happen to be in? (IF REFUSED, INTERVIEWER ESTIMATE GROUP)

a. 18 - 20	1	25/
b. 21 - 24	2	
c. 25 - 29	3	
d. 30 - 34	4	
e. 35 - 39	5	
f. 40 - 44	6	
g. 45 - 49	7	
h. 50 - 54	8	
i. 55 - 59	9	
j. 60 - 64	0	
k. 65 - 69	X	
l. 70 or older	Y	

D-17. Now here is a list of income categories. (HAND RESPONDENT CARD) Would you call off the letter of the category that best describes the combined annual income of all members of this household, including wages or salary, pensions, interest or dividends, and all other sources?

a. Under \$7,000	1	26/
b. \$7,000 to \$9,999	2	
c. \$10,000 to \$14,999	3	
d. \$15,000 to \$19,999	4	
e. \$20,000 to \$24,999	5	
f. \$25,000 to \$29,999	6	
g. \$30,000 to \$34,999	7	
h. \$35,000 to \$39,999	8	
i. \$40,000 to \$49,999	9	
j. \$50,000 to \$74,999	0	
k. \$75,000 and over	X	
Not sure/refused	Y	

D-18. Do you consider yourself to be of Hispanic origin or not?

Yes..... 1

27/

No 2

INTERVIEWER RECORD

Sex

Male 1 28/

Female 2

Race

White 1 29/

Black 2

Asian 3

Other 4

NAME _____

ADDRESS _____

APT. # _____

CITY OR TOWN _____

STATE _____

ZIP CODE _____ (30-34)

AREA CODE _____ TELE # _____ (35-44)

MONTH/DAY/YEAR _____ (45-54)

Day of week:

First Saturday 1 Wednesday 5

Sunday 2 Thursday 6

Monday 3 Friday 7

Tuesday 4 Second Saturday 8

55/

7

INTERVIEWERS NAME: _____

79-0
80-9

COLUMN

501-504
505'1,2'

ID NUMBER
X,Y VERSION
GEOGRAPHIC AREA

506'1'
506'2'
506'3'
506'4'
506'5'
506'6'
506'7'
506'8'
506'9'

NEW ENGLAND
MID-ATLANTIC
EAST NORTH CENTRAL
WEST NORTH CENTRAL
SOUTH ATLANTIC
EAST SOUTH CENTRAL
WEST SOUTH CENTRAL
MOUNTAIN
PACIFIC

CLUSTER FRAME
HAVE 507-512 AS OF RR 91-3

507-509

PSU#

SIZE

510'135,246,7,8'

CENTRAL CITY
SUBURBS
SMALL TOWN
RURAL
LARGE CITY
LARGE SUBURB
MEDIUM CITY
MEDIUM SUBURB
SMALL CITY
SMALL SUBURB
SMALL TOWN
RURAL

510'1'
510'2'
510'3'
510'4'
510'5'
510'6'
510'7'
510'8'
511-512

STATE

MARKET SIZE

513'1'
513'2'
513'3'
513'4'

A
B
C
D

514-517

WEIGHTS XX.XX

POLITICAL IDEOLOGY

520'1'
520'2'
520'3'
520'4'
520'5'
520'7'

VERY CONSERVATIVE
MODERATELY CONSERVATIVE
MIDDLE-OF-THE-ROAD
MODERATELY LIBERAL
VERY LIBERAL
CONSERVATIVE

COLUMN
520'8'
520'Y'

LIBERAL
DON'T KNOW

POLITICAL AFFILIATION

521'1'
521'2'
521'3'
521'4'
521'5'
521'6'
521'7'
521'Y'

DEMOCRAT
REPUBLICAN
OTHER SPECIFIC PARTY
INDEPENDENT
NO PARTICULAR PARTY
REFUSED
TOTAL INDEPENDENT
DON'T KNOW
DETAIL FOR POLITICAL/SOCIAL ACTIVISM

WRITTEN YOUR CONGRESSMAN/SENATOR

522'2'	ATTENDED POLITICAL RALLY/SPEECH
522'3'	ATTENDED PUBLIC MEETING
522'4'	HELD OR RUN FOR POLITICAL OFFICE
522'5'	SERVED ON A COMMITTEE
522'6'	SERVED AS AN OFFICER
522'7'	WRITTEN A LETTER TO THE PAPER
522'8'	SIGNED A PETITION
522'9'	WORKED FOR A POLITICAL PARTY
522'0'	MADE A SPEECH
522'X'	WRITTEN AN ARTICLE FOR MAG/NEWSPAPER
523'1'	BEEN MEMBER OF BETTER GOVT GROUP
523'2'	NO--NONE OF THESE
523'Y'	DON'T KNOW

EMPLOYMENT

524'1'	-----
524'2'	FULL TIME
	PART TIME

COLUMN

524'3'	NOT EMPLOYED
525'1'	HOMEMAKER
525'2'	UNEMPLOYED
525'3'	STUDENT
525'4'	RETIRED
525'5Y' SOMETIMES 5/Y	OTHER

OCCUPATION

526'1'	-----
526'2'	TOP MANAGEMENT, MAJOR PROFESSIONAL
526'3'	EXECUTIVE, ADMINISTRATIVE
526'4'	OWNER-SMALL STORE OR BUSINESS
526'5'	FARMERS (OWNERS, MANAGERS)
526'6'	TECHNICIANS, MINOR ADMIN.
526'7'	WHITE COLLAR, CLERICAL
526'8'	SALESMEN
526'9'	SKILLED AND SEMI-SKILLED
526'0'	UNSKILLED
	SERVICE & PROTECTIVE

UNION MEMBERSHIP

527'1'	-----
527'2'	UNION MEMBER
527'3'	OTHER FAMILY MEMBER ONLY
527'Y'	NO ONE BELONGS TO UNION
	DON'T KNOW

RELIGION

528'1'	-----
528'2'	PROTESTANT
528'3'	CATHOLIC
528'4'	JEWISH
528'5'	OTHER
528'Y'	NONE
	DON'T KNOW

COLUMN

MARITAL STATUS

529'1'	-----
529'2'	MARRIED
529'3'	NEVER MARRIED
529'4'	WIDOWED
	SEPARATED/DIVORCED

EMPLOYMENT OF SPOUSE

530'1'	-----
530'2'	EMPLOYED FULL TIME
530'3'	EMPLOYED PART TIME
	NOT EMPLOYED

KIDS AGE 0-17 AT HOME

531'1'	-----
532'1'	HAVE UNDER 13
	HAVE 13 TO 17

FAMILY SIZE

533'1'	ONE
533'2'	TWO
533'3'	THREE
533'4'	FOUR
533'5'	FIVE
533'6'	SIX
533'7'	SEVEN
533'8'	EIGHT
533'9'	NINE
533'X'	TEN OR MORE

COLUMN

EDUCATION

534'1'	NO SCHOOL
534'2'	GRADE SCHOOL
534'3'	SOME HIGH SCHOOL
534'4'	HIGH SCHOOL GRAD
534'5'	SOME COLLEGE
534'6'	COLLEGE GRAD
534'7'	POST GRADUATE
534'8'	SOME COLLEGE OR MORE
534'9'	NON-HIGH SCHOOL GRAD
534'0'	COLLEGE GRAD OR MORE

NOT USED

AGE

535'1'	18-20
535'2'	21-24
535'3'	25-29
535'4'	30-34
535'5'	35-39
535'6'	40-44
535'7'	45-49
535'8'	50-54
535'9'	55-59
535'0'	60-64
535'X' & 535'NY'	65-69
535'Y'	70 AND OLDER

INCOME

536'1'	UNDER \$7,000
536'2'	\$7,000-\$9,999
536'3'	\$10,000-\$14,999
536'4'	\$15,000-\$19,999
536'5'	\$20,000-\$24,999

COLUMN

536'6'	\$25,000-\$29,999
536'7'	\$30,000-\$34,999
536'8'	\$35,000-\$39,999
536'9'	\$40,000-\$49,999
536'0'	\$50,000-\$74,999
536'X'	\$75,000 & OVER
536'Y'	REFUSED

HAVE KIDS

537'1'	0-3
537'2'	4-7
537'3'	8-12
537'4'	13-17

SEX

538'1'	MALE
538'2'	FEMALE

RACE

539'1'	WHITE
539'2'	BLACK
539'4'	ASIAN AS OF 93-1
539'3'	OTHER

HISPANIC

540'1'
540'2'
541-545

YES
NO
ZIP CODE

PLAN TO GO BACK TO
WORK:

546'1'
546'2'
546'3'
546'Y'

IN A YEAR
SOMETIME
NOT AT ALL
DON'T KNOW

COLUMN

CURRENT JOB IS:

547'1'
547'2'
547'Y'

CAREER
JUST A JOB
DON'T KNOW
AGE GROUPS

549'1'
549'2'
549'3'
549'4'

18-29
30-44
45-59
60 & OVER

INCOME

549'5-8' NOT USED

OLD INCOME GROUPS

EMPLOYMENT

549'9'
549'0'
549'X'

MARRIED, ONE INCOME
MARRIED, TWO INCOMES
EMPLOYED FEMALES

POLITICAL/SOCIAL ACTIVISM
(EXCLUDES SIGNED PETITION)

549'Y'
550'1'

3 OR MORE ACTIVITIES
1 OR 2 ACTIVITIES

CHILDREN UNDER 18

550'2'
550'2'&572'N2'

HAVE KIDS 0-17 AT HOME
PARENTS OF KIDS 0-17 AT HOME

COLUMN

FAMILY SIZE

550'3'

ONE OR TWO PERSONS

OCCUPATION GROUPS

550'4'
550'5'
550'6'

EXECUTIVE/PROFESSIONAL
WHITE COLLAR
BLUE COLLAR

GEOGRAPHIC AREA

550'8'
550'9'
550'0'
550'X'

NORTHEAST
MIDWEST
SOUTH
WEST

OWN VS. RENT HOME

551'1'
551'2'
551'3'
551'4'
551'5'

OWN
RENT
LIVE WITH PARENTS
LIVE WITH CHILDREN
OTHER

WHO DOES MOST GROCERY

SHOPPING FOR HOUSEHOLD

552'1' RESPONDENT
 552'2' SOMEBODY ELSE
 552'3' SHARED EQUALLY
 552'4' NOBODY DOES
 552'Y' DON'T KNOW

HOUSEHOLD HEAD

553'1' MALE HEAD
 553'2' FEMALE HEAD
 553'3' OTHER ADULT IN HOUSEHOLD

PERSONAL COMPUTER IN HOME

553'1' OWN PC
 553'2' DO NOT OWN PC
 553'3' DON'T KNOW

HAVE KIDS AGE 0-17 AT HOME

564'1' BOTH WORK
 564'2' 0,1 WORK

PARENTS OF KIDS 0-17

564'3' BOTH WORK
 564'4' 0,1 WORK
 MARRIED/UNMARRIED

565'1' MARRIED BOTH WORK
 565'2' MARRIED 0,1 WORK
 565'3' UNMARRIED AGE <45
 565'4' UNMARRIED AGE 45+

COLUMN

INCOME GROUPS

566'1' UNDER \$15,000
 566'2' \$15,000-\$29,999
 566'3' \$30,000-\$49,999
 566'4' \$50,000 & OVER

567-568 DATE OF INTERVIEW

569'1-8' DAY OF WEEK

CABLE

570'1' HAVE CABLE
 570'2' DO NOT HAVE
 570'Y' DON'T KNOW

VCR

571'1' VCR QN DROPPED
 571'2' HAVE VCR
 571'Y' DO NOT HAVE
 DON'T KNOW

ARE YOU A PARENT?

572'1' YES
 572'2' NO

PREMIUM CABLE

573'1' HAVE PREMIUM CABLE
 573'2' DO NOT HAVE
 573'Y' DON'T KNOW

SIZE ORGANIZATION WORK FOR

574'1'
574'2'
574'3'

LARGE (500+ EMPLOYEES)
MEDIUM (40-499)
SMALL (LESS THAN 50)

SELF-EMPLOYED

575'1'
575'2'

SELF-EMPLOYED
EMPLOYED BY SOMEONE ELSE

GREEN GAUGE SEGMENTATION

577'1'
577'2'
577'3'
577'4'
577'5'
577'6'

GROUSERS
TRUE BLUE GREENS
BASIC BROWNS
NOT CATEGORIZED
SPROUTS
GREENBACK GREENS